

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

PEDAGOGICAL APPROACH TO EXPLORING GENDER BALANCE IN EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES

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ABSTRACT

Within the framework of the project "Promoting a Gender-Oriented Approach in General Education," the content of several textbook components applied at the general education level is analyzed from a gender-sensitive perspective.

The main purpose of the analysis was to determine whether gender equality is promoted in the teaching and learning materials for subjects and to look at the points that hinder it from a gender point of view. To assess gender bias in the content, a methodology document was prepared by a working group of experts based on the relevant UNESCO guide. During the evaluation, both written and descriptive examples included in the textbook sets are analyzed according to directions such as gender, profession, personality, internal and external family roles, father's and mother's roles.

Based on the obtained results, the proposed amendments and proposals were given in the recommendation document created for each fund. The recommendation document prepared by the experts is submitted to the relevant structural units of the Ministry of Education and Art for consideration in the process of improving the selected textbooks. In addition, training should be organized for representatives of publishing houses and textbook authors to maintain gender equality in the content.

It should be noted that the "promotion of gender-oriented approach in general education" project is implemented with the financial means of the UN Population Fund. Part of the project is also financed by the program "Elimination of gender-based sex selection and related harmful practices in the South Caucasus" implemented by the UN Population Fund with the support of the European Union.

Key words: gender, gender equality, high school, school textbooks, woman, man, education.

The concept of "gender", used in the social sciences of Western countries since the 1960s, is associated with the analysis of women's problems, especially the relationship between women and men in society. The idea that biological factors are sufficient for an adequate analysis of women's and men's relationships also dates back to this period. [8. Page 4]

Since the 1970s, we have encountered certain research attempts and considerations about the concept of gender in Western literature, mainly in English-language literature, and later in various countries, including currently in Azerbaijan.

In modern times, "Gender relations" conventionally refers to the mutual relations of the sexes only in the socio-cultural sphere. Although this view is not unanimously accepted. [9. Pg.8]

What is gender?

A person becomes an object of influence of the gender system from the moment of birth. In traditional societies, there are symbolic customs related to the birth of a child, clothes are chosen for the newborn child in colors appropriate to his gender, toys are bought, and it is even possible to determine the sex of the baby based on these signs without even knowing the gender of the baby. Sometimes, newborn children are treated according to their gender; for example, parents often feed newborn boys a lot, but make their girls talk more.

Gender norms are instilled in children's minds during the process of raising children in the family, in the education system, and in culture as a whole, forming certain moral rules and creating an idea of what a real man and a real woman should be like.

We describe ourselves in many ways. Most often, we base this on biological criteria, such as "I am a woman" or "I am a man." These statements can be used to make inferences about others whose faces we have never seen. The description given in this way goes beyond a simple description of human anatomy. This information not only tells us about a person's gender, but also their personal qualities and behavior. By using the above statements, people can talk about what you wear, how you express yourself, and even your life activities.

If you are a woman, they will imagine you in a dress, but they will not be surprised if they see you in trousers. It seems to many that if you are a woman, you must be relatively passive, not independent-minded, emotional, and prone to crying. You must enjoy caring for others, taking care of children, in short, selflessness, and because your appearance is very important to you, you are extremely preoccupied with it. You are not very interested in business matters, the processes going on in the world, and you do not know mechanics.

If you are a man, they will imagine you in trousers, and if they suddenly see you in a dress, they will be surprised, maybe even scared. It seems to them that if you are a man, then you are a person who is extremely stubborn, independent, and able to control your emotions. According to them, you are very serious about your work, ambitious, passionate about your work, well-versed in science, sports, business, and you are quite knowledgeable about world events and mechanics. Thus, men and women are treated differently in society according to their beliefs, and sometimes they are put against each other.

In other words, biologically assigned sex is used as the basis for constructing a social category, which we call gender: masculinity or femininity. This means that a description of your socially assigned gender character can provide a clearer picture of you than a description of yourself according to your biological sex.

Importantly, this differentiation occurs not only at the interpersonal level but also at the level of the social structure. Society draws these lines for itself, behaviors, and social interactions based on gender. These features are confirmed in the institutions of society, that is, they are reflected in the economy, politics, the educational system, religion, family, and other institutions. This institutionalized model of gender differentiation is attributed to the sex-gender system in society.

The sex-gender system has historically manifested itself in various ways, both in mixed cultures and in other cultures. However, in each system, at least three interacting components are necessarily present:

- a) The social construction of gender categories based on biological sex;
- b) The division of labor by sex, in which specific tasks are divided and performed primarily by sex;
- c) The social regulation of sexuality, in which specific forms of sexual expression are sanctioned either positively or negatively.

The construction of gender is polar and contradictory. Social norms change from time to time, while gender asymmetry remains constant.

The sex-gender system functions as a social stratification of women and men; their behaviors and characteristics are evaluated unequally in society. Human consciousness plays an important role in the maintenance and development of the gender system. The construction of individuals' gender consciousness occurs through the support and dissemination of social and cultural stereotypes and norms, and society punishes people for their mistakes.

In social institutions, rewards and punishments are assigned, privileges are given as rewards, obligations and prohibitions are determined according to the sex of people. The gender system has a huge impact on the lives and lifestyles of women and men. At this point, it would be appropriate to recall a point from the report of the UN Commission on the Status of Women in 1980: "Considering that women constitute approximately 60% of the world's population, they perform two-thirds of the work done. However, they receive one-tenth of the world's income, and less than 1% of the world's property belongs to those who have it." Even after more than three decades since the mentioned statistics, no significant change is noticeable in the figures given. Such surprising facts reflect the situation of women and men in a society where the patriarchal gender system exists. Patriarchy is a gender system in which men dominate in society, and masculinity is valued higher than femininity. Feminists, on the other hand, prefer an egalitarian society, which is considered the opposite of patriarchal society and is based on the principles of gender equality. This is a society in which every right and opportunity that belongs to men should be available to women. It should also be noted that not all men benefit equally from a patriarchal society, but

it is also a fact that in such a society, women have fewer advantages than men. [1. Pg. 1821].

§1. Gender and education.

Education makes us respectable and helps us understand and hold our rightful place in society. Education makes us understand our social status and gives us the strength and skills to improve it.

People go to school at a certain age to get an education. What is the need for a person for this? If there is such a need, then what responsibility does the school have? The school is primarily a provider of knowledge and skills that students need to properly fulfill their various roles in society in their future lives. In addition to knowledge and skills, the school is also responsible for teaching students social, political, and economic values that play an important role in their future lives.

There is a curriculum for systematic education in schools. There are two types of curriculum, one is the open curriculum that students see, and the other is the hidden curriculum that students do not see, but is actively used in school and known by every teacher. Through the first, lessons are taught based on the materials given in books. The other is implemented explicitly. The second is more about regulating the behavior of students than knowledge. The issue of regulating behavior is also often carried out according to gender. For example, girls and boys are rewarded differently for work that is considered good at the same level, or, conversely, girls and boys are punished differently for the results of work that is considered bad. Observing all this, girls and boys are educated by stereotyping themselves without knowing it.

In general, education is a means to a high status education gives a person respect. The main goal of education is to help people find their rightful place in society. Sometimes their place is determined according to their gender. As we have said, education is very important for a high status and self-affirmation in society, but it is even more important for women. In a patriarchal society, an educated woman ensures her rights and entitlements in a way. With the help of education, individuals can make the right choices in their economic, social, and political lives. The education system is a determinant of gender norms and, most importantly, the sex-gender system. Perhaps for this reason, even in the past, when education was inaccessible to women, many women joined the struggle for education.

What do they teach in school? Fundamental cultural values, including gender norms, should be taught in schools and school programs, along with science.

As we mentioned above, there are two types of curriculum in education: While the open curriculum is the teaching that teachers teach purely through teaching materials, the hidden curriculum is the teaching and upbringing that is indirectly taught and instilled. Through the first, lessons are taught, analyzed, is reinforced, that is, students are taught the secrets of science. Through the second, moral rules are dictated, and social roles, traditional gender roles are instilled. According to critics of education, the hidden curriculum still supports traditional gender roles. Girls who do not properly adhere to gender roles are suppressed during education and forced to listen to the conversation "how a real girl

should be." In other words, as we have noted, boys and girls who do essentially the same actions in the educational process are treated differently.

Starting from primary school, if you look at textbooks, you will see the same thing in textbooks, where there is little space for articles about women. There are enough articles about male heroes in Azerbaijani history in textbooks. Women are either mentioned very little, or when they are mentioned, it is observed with male dominance, or at best, women are presented as assistants to men. Even during the Soviet era, when it came to good women, most textbooks praised women who were loyal to their families, children, family, and traditions; that is, it was always emphasized that they were more suitable for the private sphere. Despite regular reforms in education, girls were instilled with the idea that their future adequate place was mainly in the family.

Of course, textbooks accompanied by male bias have not remained without an impact on the identification of girls and boys. These books not only preserve traditionalism, but also serve to limit the role of women in modern social life. The image of a real woman in textbooks is described as follows: The ideal woman is a woman who is a good wife, a good mother, selfless, capable of providing care, etc. Such an idea, formed in girls and boys at an early age, ultimately directly affects their gender roles and slows down their socio-political development. Even when elementary school students are asked what jobs women or men can work in, they attribute all prestigious, high-paying jobs to men and monotonous, low-perspective, low-paying jobs to women. Students who receive messages in line with gender stereotypes in the educational process end up with very contradictory ideas and face difficulties when choosing a specialty. On the one hand, the ideas that are voiced about the existence of gender equality in a democratic society, and on the other hand, the ideas propagated about the real woman of society confuse their thinking. Thus, girls understand that the best student should never forget her gender role and should not give up her femininity. In general, girls are instilled from childhood, sometimes explicitly, sometimes implicitly, with the idea that the equivalent of happiness is a successful marriage.

Students hear a lot about which subjects are masculine and which are feminine from an early age at school. Girls who love mathematics, physics, and chemistry often have doubts about their femininity, and the idea that these subjects are more suitable for boys does not leave them. Do not think that gender messages are transmitted only to girls. Parents who are forced to make a choice when it comes to investing in science and education, without thinking, give preference to their sons. There is injustice and non-objectivity at the heart of such an approach. [5. Pg. 21-22].

§2. Measures aimed at eliminating discrimination in education.

Article 10 of the UN Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women states that "States Parties shall take all appropriate measures to eliminate discrimination against women to

ensure to them, on a basis of equality of men and women, the following rights in the field of education:"

Article 13 of the Law on Guarantees of Gender Equality states the following:

- The state shall ensure the creation of equal opportunities for men and women to exercise the right to education.
- The employer shall create equal conditions for men and women to receive basic and additional education, and to use the right to educational leave.
- The state shall ensure the creation of equal opportunities for men and women in admission to all educational institutions, in providing students with scholarships, in selecting the curriculum, and in assessing knowledge, regardless of the type of ownership.
- Textbooks shall be based on the principle of gender equality.

Article 5.3 of the Law on Education states that "The state, regardless of the form of ownership, ensures equal opportunities for men and women in recruitment, appointment or selection to positions, labor incentives, admission to educational institutions, provision of scholarships to students, selection of specialties, assessment of knowledge, employment of graduates, continuation of education at the next level, improvement of qualifications and other issues in the field of education". As can be seen, the Law on Guarantees of Gender Equality repeats the relevant article of the Law on Education. Both laws contain provisions on equal opportunities for women to access education and to carry out labor activities in the field of education. In addition, the Labor Code also contains provisions on the creation of equal rights and opportunities for women and men in recruitment and labor relations, which were discussed above.

The UN Convention, in addition to creating a legislative basis for women and men to have equal rights in education, as in all other areas, also raises the issue of ensuring that they have equal opportunities both in receiving and in the field of education, and at the same time, this equality is ensured.

However, although the Law on Gender Equality, the Law on Education, etc., legislative norms establish equal rights for women and men in the field of education, the mechanisms for implementing these norms are not perfect. The laws do not have provisions and mechanisms that could ensure equality for women in the field of education. The educational indicators of women in the country can be considered high. Thus, according to the latest population census, 76.8% of women aged 20-54 in Azerbaijan have complete secondary education, 11.7% have secondary specialized education, 12.5% have higher education, 6.9% have general secondary education, and 1% have primary education. The educational indicator among women over 15 years of age is 99.7%.

While more than 80% of employees working in the field of education are women, this high indicator is not maintained in the management of education, including in leadership positions in the field of education. Men predominate in leadership positions in the field of education, and this is the case at all levels. In this regard, the relevant legislation has not been able to ensure

full equality in the field of education. For example, Article 13.4 of the Law states that "Textbooks must be based on the principle of gender equality". However, materials specifically promoting and encouraging the principles of gender equality during the preparation of textbooks are not sufficient. In general, an examination of the suitability of textbooks in terms of promoting gender equality is not conducted. In general, gender culture is aimed at weakening "patriarchal values", including the dominant position of one gender in family and household relations, and there are no systematic activities to form this culture.

Recommendations

The Law on Guarantees of Gender Equality, the Law on Education, and other relevant normative legal acts should include provisions aimed at the actual provision of these rights, in addition to equal rights for women regarding access to education and careers in the field of education. In this regard, it is also appropriate to provide for temporary positive measures.

When developing textbooks, special expertise should be provided to ensure that they are based on the principles of gender equality. The current textbooks are neither necessary nor sufficiently adapted to the study and promotion of the principles of gender equality and women's participation. [7. Pg. 9].

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